

Existence of odd prime divisors of sums of squares of two different non zero integers

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Subject : theorem with proof

Title:

Existence of odd prime divisors of sums of squares of two different non zero integers

Abstract: this work has three parts.

Part 1: The Theorem :

Every whole number, sum of squares of two different non zero integers has at least one odd prime divisor, itself sum of squares of two integers prime between themselves.

i, e : $\forall a, b : a \neq 0, b \neq 0, a \neq b \exists p \neq 2$ prime number : $p = x^2 + y^2, p/a^2 + b^2$ for some integers x, y prime between themselves. (with proof)

Part 2: property -1- (with proof).

Let $a; b$ two integers prime between themselves. we have: either $a^2 + b^2 = 2N$ for some odd number N , or $a^2 + b^2 = 2N + 1$ for some non zero integer N

Property -2- (with proof).

Let p be a prime number: $p \neq 2$

If $p = x^2 + y^2$ for some integers $x; y$ then x and y are prime between themselves

Part 3: three theorems (Fermat's theorems and Euler's theorems)**Theorem 1 :**

Every number which divides a Sum of squares of two integers prime between themselves is itself sum of squares of two integers. (without proof)

Theorem 2 :

Every prime number of the form $4n + 1$ (n non zero integer) can be written as a sum of squares of two integers in only one way (without proof)

Theorem 3 :

a prime number of the form $4n + 3$ (n integer) cannot be written as a sum of two squares of two integers. (without proof).

Keywords : odd prime ; divisors ; sum of squares ; prime between themselves ; different ; non zero integers

note that " prime between themselves" means coprime.

Preface

This is a theorem proven by me.

Hope it will contribute to the progress of mathematics.

*I dedicate this work to every lover of pure mathematics
in the world.*

Habib Lebsir

Theorem:

Every whole number, sum of squares of two different non zero integers, has at least one odd and prime divisor, itself sum of squares of two integers prime between themselves.

i. e: $\forall a, b : a \neq 0, b \neq 0, a \neq b$

$\exists \rho \neq 2$ Prime number

$$\rho = x^2 + y^2, \rho / a^2 + b^2$$

For some integers x, y prime between themselves

The proof of this theorem calls upon the followings:

Property ①:

Let a, b two integers prime between themselves.

We have:

Either: $a^2 + b^2 = 2N$ for some odd number N

Or: $a^2 + b^2 = 4N + 1$ for some non zero integer N

Proof: since a and b are prime between themselves they can't be both even integers: thus either both a and b are odd integers.

i. e $a = 2k + 1, b = 2k' + 1$ for some integer k and k'

Then: $a^2 + b^2 = (2k + 1)^2 + (2k' + 1)^2 = 4k^2 + 4k'^2 + 4k + 4k' + 2 = (2k^2 + 2k'^2 + 2k + 2k' + 1) = 2N$

with: $2k^2 + 2k'^2 + 2k + 2k' + 1 = N$

N is an odd integer.

Or : a is even, b is odd.

i. e: $a = 2k, b = 2k' + 1$ for some integers k , and $k' (k \neq 0)$

Then : $a^2 + b^2 = 4k^2 + 4k'^2 + 4k' + 1 = 4(k^2 + k'^2 + k') + 1 = 4N + 1$ with : $N = k^2 + k'^2 + k'$

(N is a non zero integer because $k \neq 0$).

Property ②

Let p be a prime number: $p \neq 2$.

If $p = x^2 + y^2$ for some integers x, y .

Then: x and y are prime between themselves

Proof: Indeed if $d \neq 1$ is a common divisor of x and y we will have:

$$x = dx', y = dy', x^2 + y^2 = d^2(x'^2 + y'^2)$$

Then: d^2/p which is prime.

Thus $d^2 = p$.

Hence $1, d$ and d^2 would be divisors of p Absurd! (Because p is prime)

Theorem ①

Every number which divides a sum of squares of two integers prime between themselves is itself sum of squares of two integers

Theorem ②

Every prime number of the form $4n + 1$ (n non zero integer) can be written as a sum of squares of two integers in only one way

Theorem ③

A prime number of the form $4n + 3$ (n Integer) can not be written as a sum of two squares of two integers

Proof of the theorem

✓ Notice that if $(a \neq 0, b \neq 0)$ then $a^2 + b^2 \neq 1$ ($a^2 + b^2 \geq 2$).

The proof has two parts

☞ **Part one:** a and b are not prime between themselves i.e : $gcd(a, b) = \Delta \neq 1$

We have $a = \Delta a' \rightarrow a^2 = \Delta^2 a'^2$

$b = \Delta b' \rightarrow b^2 = \Delta^2 b'^2$

$a^2 + b^2 = \Delta^2(a'^2 + b'^2)$

If $(a'^2 + b'^2)$ is prime then the problem is solved; $(a'^2 + b'^2) | a'^2 + b'^2$ and $a'^2 + b'^2$ is sum of two squares a' and b' prime between themselves

If $a'^2 + b'^2$ is not prime.

Either: $a'^2 + b'^2 = 2N$ with N odd number; $N/a'^2 + b'^2$ and so $N/a^2 + b^2$

If N is prime, N is a sum of squares of two integers (see theorem ①)

These two integers are prime between themselves (see property ②)

if: N is not prime :

Then all its prime factors are $(4n + 1)$ prime numbers because a $(4n + 3)$ prime number can not divide $(a'^2 + b'^2)$ otherwise, it would be written as a sum of squares of two integers. (see theorem ③)

So: all the prime factors of $a'^2 + b'^2$ are sums of squares of two integers prime between themselves (see theorem ① and property ②)

Or: $a^2 + b^2 = 4N + 1$: then all its prime factors are $4n+1$ prime numbers and thus squares of two different non zero Integer prime between themselves (see theorems ② and ③ and property ②)

☞ **Finally:** if a and b are not prime between themselves $(a^2 + b^2)$ has at least one odd and prime divisor sum of squares of two integers prime between themselves.

Examples :

1) $18^2 + 12^2 = 6^2(3^2 + 2^2) = 6^2 \cdot 13$

13 is prime ; $\gcd(3,2) = 1$

$\gcd(18,12) = 6.$

2) $2^2 + 6^2 = 2^2(1^2 + 3^2) = 2^2 \times 10 = 2^2 \times 2 \times 5 = 2^3 \times 5$; $5 = 1^2 + 2^2$; $\gcd(1,2) = 1$

3) $20^2 + 15^2 = 5^2(4^2 + 3^2) = 5^2 \times 25 = 5^2 \times 5^2 = 5^4(5 = 1^2 + 2^2)$, $\gcd(20,15) = 5$ $\gcd(1,2) = 1$

4) $12^2 + 21^2 = 3^2(4^2 + 7^2) = 3^2 \times 65 = 3^2 \times 13 \times 5$ $\gcd(12,21) = 3$

$13 = 3^2 + 2^2$; $\gcd(3,2) = 1$

$5 = 1^2 + 2^2$; $\gcd(1,2) = 1$

Part two : a and b prime between themselves**Section A** : a and b are both odd numbers.

$a = 2k + 1$, $b = 2k' + 1$ then :

$a^2 + b^2 = 2N$ with N is an odd number (see property ①)

 $N/a^2 + b^2$ then N is sum of squares of two integers x, y If N is prime : then x, y are prime between themselves (see property ②)**If N is not prime :**Since N is an odd number, all its prime number factors are $(4n + 1)$ prime numbers because $(4n + 3)$ prime numbers can not divide $a^2 + b^2$ otherwise they would be sums of squares**Thus** : all prime factors of N are sums of squares of two integers prime between themselves (see property ②)**Examples:**

1) $3^2 + 5^2 = 34 = 2 \times 17 = 2(1^2 + 4^2)$; $\gcd(3,5) = 1$, $\gcd(1,4) = 1$; $N = 17$

2) $11^2 + 9^2 = 202 = 2 \times (101) = 2 \times (1^2 + 10^2)$; $\gcd(11,9) = 1$, $\gcd(1,10) = 1$; $N = 101$

3) $3^2 + 11^2 = 130 = 2 \times 65$; $\gcd(3,11) = 1$, $N = 65 = 5 \times 13$

$5 = 1^2 + 2^2$; $\gcd(1,2) = 1$

$13 = 2^2 + 3^2$; $\gcd(2,3) = 1$

Section B: a is even, b is odd.

i.e : $a = 2k$; $b = 2k' + 1$ with k, k' integers, $k \neq 0$.

Them: $a^2 + b^2 = 4n + 1$ For some non-zero integer n (see property ①)If $4n + 1$ is not prime. $4n + 1$ is an odd number then all its prime factors are $(4n + 1)$ prime numbers because $(4n + 3)$ prime numbers can not divide $a^2 + b^2$, otherwise they would be sums of squares of two integers (see theorem ③)**Therefore**: all its prime factors are sums of squares of two integers prime between themselves (see property ① and property ②).

Examples :

1) $2^2 + 3^2 = 13$; $\gcd(2,3) = 1$

13 is prime

2) $2^2 + 11^2 = 125 = 5^3(5 = 1^2 + 2^2)$; $\gcd(2,11) = 1$ $\gcd(1,2) = 1$

3) $6^2 + 7^2 = 85 = 5 \times 17$; $\gcd(6,7) = 1$, $17 = 1^2 + 4^2$; $\gcd(1,4) = 1$
 $5 = 1^2 + 2^2$; $\gcd(1,2) = 1$

Finally: the theorem is proven

➤ The theorems ①, ② and ③ have been proven by Leonhard Euler and Pierre de Fermat.